

Introducing Implicit Tube Model Predictive Control to MPT+: Efficient Design for Large-Scale Systems

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Abstract—As society advances, increasingly complex systems pose new challenges for control engineers. To address these challenges, researchers continually develop state-of-the-art control techniques. This creates a demand for software tools that integrate these advanced methods and allow users to utilize them with ease. In this paper, we aim to enhance the MPT+ toolbox, an extension of the widely used Multi-Parametric Toolbox (MPT), with a novel implicit tube Model Predictive Control (MPC) approach. This approach avoids geometric set operations and enables robust MPC designs for large-scale problems. It will be shown that MPT+ allows users to apply this control strategy within a few lines in a user-friendly manner. Moreover, via a case study, we demonstrate that the implicit tube MPC approach enables us to design robust controllers for more complex systems, which were previously computationally intractable with the commonly used rigid tube MPC methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

Model Predictive Control (MPC) [1] is a widely recognized optimal control strategy that has gained substantial traction over the past few decades, both in academia and industry [2], [3]. Although MPC has been extensively researched, challenges remain in broadening its industrial adoption. A critical factor in addressing these challenges lies in the availability of specialized validation tools. While numerous software packages support MPC design, this paper focuses explicitly on the MATLAB environment. For a broader review of MPC solvers and tools in other programming languages such as Python and Julia, refer to [4], [5], [6] and their references.

MATLAB’s commercial MPC Toolbox [7] supports various MPC design frameworks, including adaptive, explicit, gain-scheduled, and nonlinear controllers. It features built-in solvers and the MPC Designer App, a user-friendly interface for controller tuning. Nonlinear MPC problems are efficiently solved using the ACADO Toolkit [8], which employs a sequential quadratic programming approach. ACADO generates C/C++ code and provides MATLAB integration. CasADi [9] is another open-source toolbox suitable for nonlinear MPC design, supporting both MATLAB and Python. Additional open-source tools like MATMPC [10] and YALMIP [11], a popular modeling parser, also facilitate MPC design, particularly for nonlinear optimization problems. Multi-Parametric Toolbox (MPT) [12] in MATLAB is widely used for implicit

and explicit MPC design, multi-parametric optimization, and convex set operations, integrating various tools for the efficient construction and validation of advanced MPC controllers.

The MPT toolbox was enhanced in [13], introducing robust MPC design for linear time-invariant (LTI) systems affected by parametric and/or additive disturbances. While MPT incorporates advanced methods like forward/backward robust invariant set evaluations, worst-case robust MPC design remains computationally intensive, especially for large systems, as complexity increases with the number of decision variables and the prediction horizon length.

Tube MPC [14], [15] is a widely adopted robust MPC approach. Rather than accounting for all possible future disturbances, it optimizes the nominal initial state and robustifies the MPC problem by introducing a robust positively invariant set known as the tube. This approach has been extended in several directions, including homothetic tubes [16], elastic tubes [17], state estimation with output feedback [18], reference tracking [19], and parallel explicit tube MPC [20]. However, the scalability of tube MPC can be challenging, as higher-dimensional control problems require complex set operations.

A more recent development, implicit tube MPC [21], is better suited for large-scale optimization problems as it avoids geometric set operations. This approach broadens the applicability of tube MPC in complex systems. The increasing interest in tube MPC highlights the need for a user-friendly design tool that simplifies its implementation. Such a tool would allow researchers to focus on extending the original control method.

The MPT+ [22], an open-source MATLAB-based toolbox¹, extends the widely recognized MPT by introducing advanced MPC formulations. It provides users with access to state-of-the-art methodologies in both embedded and robust control. In this paper, we present the integration of the implicit tube MPC design into MPT+. Specifically, we provide the theoretical background of this approach and highlight its key differences from the commonly used rigid tube MPC method. Despite its complex formulation, we demonstrate that the implicit tube MPC policy can be implemented with just a few lines of code, significantly simplifying the process for users. This reduces the need for extensive mathematical prototyping,

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¹More information about MPT+ releases, features, and examples can be found in <https://github.com/holaza/mptplus/wiki>.

allowing users to focus more on tuning and analyzing the underlying control strategy. Finally, through a case study, we show that the implicit tube MPC is suitable for more complex systems that were previously intractable using rigid tube approaches.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUNDS

This section provides a brief review of the essential theoretical foundations of the standard MPT design, rigid tube MPC design [14], and the implicit tube MPC approach [21].

A. MPC design

Consider an uncertain linear time-invariant (ULTI) system expressed as follows:

$$x(t + T_s) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + Ed(t), \quad (1)$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ represents the system matrix, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u}$ is the input matrix, and $E \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ is the disturbance matrix, where we assume that the pair (A, B) is stabilizable. Next, $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$, $d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ are the state, input, and disturbance vectors, respectively, given in the discrete-time instant t sampled with T_s .

Assume (1) to be subjected to

$$x(t) \in \mathbb{X}, \quad u(t) \in \mathbb{U}, \quad d(t) \in \mathbb{D} \quad \forall t \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbb{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $\mathbb{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$, and $\mathbb{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ are polytopes containing the origin in their strict interiors. For future purposes, let us denote the disturbance set as

$$\mathbb{D} = \{d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x} : e_i^\top d(t) \leq 1, i = 1, \dots, N_D\}, \quad (3)$$

where N_D is the number of half-spaces representing the polytope.

For the system (1), restricted by (2), a stabilizing MPC policy can be defined as:

$$\min_{u_0, x_0, w_0, \dots, u_{N-1}, x_N, w_{N-1}} \|x_N\|_P^2 + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (\|x_k\|_Q^2 + \|u_k\|_R^2) \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } x_0 = x(t), \quad (4b)$$

$$x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k + d_k, \quad (4c)$$

$$x_k \in \mathbb{X}, u_k \in \mathbb{U}, \quad (4d)$$

$$w_k \in \mathbb{D}, \quad (4e)$$

$$x_N \in \mathbb{X}_N, \quad (4f)$$

where the quadratic cost function defined in (4a) is minimized considering the symmetric positive definite penalty matrices $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$, $R \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u \times n_u}$, and the Lyapunov matrix $P \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$. Next, $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $u_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$, and $d_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ denote state, input, and disturbance vectors, respectively, at prediction steps $k = 0, \dots, N-1$, where N is the prediction horizon. Constraints (4d)-(4e), and the model dynamics in (4c), are imposed for all prediction steps $k = 0, \dots, N-1$. The set $\mathbb{X}_N \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is designed to be a positive invariant w.r.t the closed-loop system $x(t + T_s) = (A + BK)x(t)$ and satisfying constraints (2), where $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u \times n_x}$ is a stabilizing LQ-optimal gain. For future purposes, we note that by plugging the LQ-optimal feedback law $u(t) = -Kx(t)$ into our system (1),

we obtain an autonomous system of form

$$x(t + T_s) = (A + BK)x(t) + d(t). \quad (5)$$

Commonly used approaches, how to formulate and solve MPC policies such as in (4), are, e.g., the *min-max* method [13] or a tube MPC design. In what follows, we introduce the implicit tube MPC design methodology.

B. Implicit tube MPC design

Although the tube MPC represents a well-established robust control strategy, its application range is limited. Specifically, when considering the set-based tube MPC design, this approach relies on a rigid tube

$$\mathbb{T} = \{x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x} : Cx(t) \leq 1\} \quad (6)$$

that is constructed as a minimal robust positive invariant (RPI) set w.r.t. (5), i.e., such that $(A + BK)\mathbb{T} \oplus \mathbb{W} \subseteq \mathbb{T}$ holds and where \oplus denotes the Minkowski sum. The algorithm to construct \mathbb{T} can be found in [23]. Subsequently, by utilizing this tube \mathbb{T} , the optimization problem (4) is then robustified via using several set-based geometrical operations. Consequently, implementing tube MPC is challenging for complex, large-scale uncertain systems.

To prevent these geometrical set-based operations, the implicit tube MPC algorithm introduced in [21] reformulates the original RPI set \mathbb{T} into its *implicit* time-varying representation $\mathcal{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{T} = (1 - \alpha)^{-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N_S-1} (A + BK)^j \omega_j, \quad (7)$$

where

$$e_i^\top \omega_j \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_D, \quad j = 1, \dots, N_S, \quad (8)$$

and the sequence of uncertainties ω is derived from the original uncertain parameters (3), i.e., $\omega_j \in \mathbb{D}$. Obviously, this sequence aligns with the iterative procedure of constructing the tube, comprising of N_S steps, where $\omega_j \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ for $j = 1, \dots, N_S$. However, in the implicit approach, the geometric tube is not explicitly constructed in advance. Instead, the optimized vectors ω from the original set \mathbb{D} are utilized, which are influenced by N_S steps of the dynamics $(A + BK)$, resulting in specific vertices of the original tube \mathbb{T} . Consequently, the tube MPC subjects the difference between the first optimized state vector \hat{x}_0 and the current state measurement $x(t)$ to be within proximity of the tube \mathcal{T} , i.e.,

$$x(t) - \hat{x}_0 = \mathcal{T}. \quad (9)$$

For the simplicity of notation, the implicit tube \mathcal{T} is projected to the constraints in (4d) using a vector $f \in \mathbb{R}^{N_C}$, where N_C is number of constraints, resulting in the following equivalent statements:

$$(\hat{x}_k \times \hat{u}_k) \in ((\mathbb{X} \ominus \mathbb{T}) \times (\mathbb{U} \ominus K \cdot \mathbb{T})), \quad (10a)$$

$$c_l^\top \hat{x}_k + d_l^\top \hat{u}_k \leq 1 - f_l, \quad l = 1, \dots, N_C. \quad (10b)$$

The auxiliary vector $f \in \mathbb{R}^{N_C}$, which is precomputed in advance and signifies the projection of the implicit tube into the state and input constraints, thereby effectively shrinking the shape of the original sets \mathbb{X} and \mathbb{U} . This robustification of the constraints using the auxiliary

vector f is defined as follows:

$$f_l = (1 - \alpha)^{-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N_S-1} h \left(\mathbb{D}, \left((A + BK)^j \right)^\top \eta_l \right), \quad (11a)$$

$$\eta_l = c_l + K^\top d_l, l = 1, \dots, N_C, \quad (11b)$$

where h is the support function.

Analogous, the terminal constraint in (4f) is reformulated using the vector f :

$$(c_l^\top + d_l^\top K) \hat{x}_N \leq 1 - f_l, \quad l = 1, \dots, N_C. \quad (12)$$

The implicit tube \mathcal{T} in (7) and the constraints robustification using the auxiliary vector f in (10) do not involve the Minkowski sum operation, i.e., the geometrical set-based operations. We recall that this was the main limiting factor when applying the tube MPC policy that utilized the rigid tube (6). Finally, the original MPC problem in (4) can be reformulated using the implicit tube MPC approach according to [21] as follows:

$$\min_{\hat{u}_0, \hat{x}_0, \omega_0, \dots, \hat{u}_{N-1}, \hat{x}_N, \omega_{N_S}} \|\hat{x}_N\|_P^2 + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (\|\hat{x}_k\|_Q^2 + \|\hat{u}_k\|_R^2) \quad (13a)$$

$$\text{s.t. : } x(t) - \hat{x}_0 = \mathcal{T}, \quad (13b)$$

$$\hat{x}_{k+1} = A\hat{x}_k + B\hat{u}_k, \quad (13c)$$

$$c_l^\top \hat{x}_k + d_l^\top \hat{u}_k \leq 1 - f_l, \quad (13d)$$

$$e_i^\top \omega_j \leq 1, \quad (13e)$$

$$(c_l^\top + d_l^\top K) \hat{x}_N \leq 1 - f_l, \quad (13f)$$

$$i = 1, \dots, N_D, \quad (13g)$$

$$j = 1, \dots, N_S, \quad (13h)$$

$$k = 0, \dots, N - 1, \quad (13i)$$

$$l = 1, \dots, N_C, \quad (13j)$$

where the problem is initialized by the state measurement $x(t)$ and vector of optimized variables are \hat{u} , \hat{x} , and ω . The closed-loop control law is then defined as

$$\kappa(x(t)) = \hat{u}_0^* + K(x(t) - \hat{x}_0^*), \quad (14)$$

where the symbol \star indicates the solution to the optimization problem presented in (13), and $\mathbb{X}_F \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ denotes the corresponding domain, which is the feasibility set for the optimized initial conditions \hat{x}_0 as specified in (13).

We would like to note that due to the implicit representation of the tube \mathcal{T} in (7), the optimization problem of implicit tube MPC design introduces N_S additional decision variables ω representing the additive disturbance. Meanwhile, the original rigid tube MPC design prevents this problem by using geometrical set-based operations that are delegated offline to the construction part. On the other hand, the implicit formulation in (13) benefits not only from its applicability for large-scale complex uncertain systems but also from the ability for real-time tuning of the performance criteria.

III. IMPLICIT TUBE MPC DESIGN IN MPT+

This section briefly introduces the main benefits of implicit tube MPC design using the recent update of

MPT+ package² and demonstrates its usage from the user's perspective.

A. Installation

The MPT+ package can be conveniently installed using `tbxManager`³ as follows:

```
tbxmanager install mptplus
```

Alternatively, users can install the MPTplus package manually and configure the appropriate path in MATLAB. Note MPT+ relies on the MPT [12] toolbox, hence both open-source packages need to be installed.

B. Illustrative example

Consider the ULTI state-space system defined in (1) to be a well-known 2D benchmark system of double integrator [14] with the system matrices in the following form:

$$x(t + T_s) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} x(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} u(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} d(t). \quad (15)$$

and initialized from $x(0) = [-5, -2]^\top$. The ULTI system is intuitively defined using MPT3 toolbox by executing the following command:

```
model = ULTISystem('A', [1, 1; 0, 1], ...
                  'B', [0.5; 1], ...
                  'E', [1, 0; 0, 1])
x0 = [-5; -2]
```

Let all variables in the system (15) be constraints by:

$$[-200, -2]^\top \leq x(t) \leq [200, 2]^\top, \quad (16a)$$

$$-1 \leq u(t) \leq 1, \quad (16b)$$

$$[-0.1, -0.1]^\top \leq d(t) \leq [0.1, 0.1]^\top. \quad (16c)$$

Using MPT3 toolbox, the physical constraints and bounds of the additive disturbance in (16) are defined as follows:

```
model.x.min = [-200; -2]
model.x.max = [ 200;  2]
model.u.min = -1
model.u.max =  1
model.d.min = [-0.1; -0.1]
model.d.max = [ 0.1;  0.1]
```

The state and control input penalty matrices, set as $Q = I$ and $R = 0.01$, can be included to the MPT formulation via:

```
model.x.penalty=QuadFunction([1, 0; 0, 1])
model.u.penalty=QuadFunction(0.01)
```

The LQ-optimal controller K , Lyapunov matrix P , and the terminal set \mathbb{X}_N can be defined manually, see the MPT+ wiki page, or automatically computed and integrated through optional parameter "LQRstability" set to value "1". Moreover, by default, the tube MPC is constructed

²MPT+: <https://github.com/holaza/mptplus>

³tbxManager: <https://www.tbxmanager.com>

in the conventional manner, i.e., as a rigid tube MPC formulation. To construct implicit tube MPC, setting the parameter “TubeType” option to “implicit” is necessary:

```
option = {'TubeType', 'implicit', ...
         'LQRstability', 1}
```

Finally, by setting our prediction horizon

```
N = 9
```

we have provided all necessary parameters of (13). To construct and evaluate the implicit tube MPC controller, the MPT+ package is invoked by calling:

```
implicit_MPC = TMPCController(model, N,
                             option)
u = implicit_MPC.evaluate(x0)
```

resulting in the optimal control action $u_0^* = 1$ for the given initial condition $x(0)$.

The closed-loop simulation for 12 control steps is simply analyzed by:

```
Nsim = 12
CLdata = implicit_MPC.simulate(x0, Nsim)
```

The resulting data structure contains all data, including the closed-loop profiles of control inputs (CLdata.U), system states (CLdata.X), and additive disturbances (CLdata.D).

We note that no additional inputs from a user are required to construct the tube optimization problem (13), i.e., all essential parameters, such as $N_S = 9$ and $\alpha = 1.9435 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in (7), were computed automatically.

Although the MPT+ offers the possibility to construct a multiparametric (explicit) controller from the implicit tube MPC using the `toExplicit` function, this approach is impractical. The implicit tube MPC is beneficial for large-scale uncertain systems where conventional geometrical set-based operations are numerically intractable due to the complexity of the resulting optimization problem. Consequently, creating a multiparametric solution for tube MPC is frequently impractical or impossible. Otherwise, in case a multiparametric (explicit) solution is available, it is recommended to design a conventional rigid tube MPC design approach.

IV. CASE STUDY

This case study focuses on a numerical simulation of implicit tube MPC applied to a large-scale system. The aim is to validate the implementation of implicit tube MPC using MPT+ in a context where constructing the original set-based tube MPC is not numerically tractable.

A. Reactor-separator plant

The case study was conducted using a well-known benchmark system adopted from [24, chap. 6.6]. This process is shown in Fig. 2 and involves three vessels: two

TABLE I: Steady-state values of the state and manipulated variables.

i	T_i^s [K]	$c_{A,i}^s$ [kmol/m ³]	$c_{B,i}^s$ [kmol/m ³]	$c_{C,i}^s$ [kmol/m ³]	H_i^s [kJ/h]
1	369.53	3.31	0.17	0.04	0
2	435.25	2.74	0.44	0.11	0
3	435.25	2.88	0.49	0.12	0

continuously stirred tank reactors and a tank separator. Within the reactors, two reactions occur simultaneously. The first reaction involves converting the reactant A into the primary product B , while the second is an undesired reaction that converts the product A into a side product C . The reactant A is introduced into the first reactor via the feed stream F_{10} . The outlet from the first reactor, denoted as F_1 , is combined with additional feed containing reactant A from the stream F_{20} to form the inlet to the second reactor. The products generated in the second reactor are directed to the separator, where the vapors are condensed and returned to the first reactor through the stream F_r . The bottom product is subsequently removed via the stream F_3 . A comprehensive description of the reactor-separator plant and the derivation of the mathematical model that captures the dynamics of all three devices can be found in [24, chap. 6.6].

Given that the process exhibits one unstable and two stable steady-state values [24, chap. 6.6], the control objective is to direct the state variables—namely, the temperatures (T_i) and the concentrations of the reactant A , as well as the products B and C : ($c_{A,i}, c_{B,i}, c_{C,i}$)—toward the optimal setpoint corresponding to the unstable steady-state specified in Table I in deviation form. Here, the subscript $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ denotes the first reactor, the second reactor, and the separator, respectively. In this case study, the control inputs are the heat flows H_1 , H_2 , and H_3 , which represent the external heat added to or removed from the tanks. The steady-state values for the system’s state variables and control inputs across all subsystems are taken from [24, chap. 6.6].

B. Control setup

The tube MPC is tuned with respect to the constraints $[-3, -3.5, -1.4]^\top \cdot 10^4 \leq u \leq [3, 3.5, 1.4]^\top \cdot 10^4$, $-x^s \leq x$, $-0.002I \leq d \leq 0.002I$,

where I represents the identity vector. The stated variables and constraint values, with the exception of the system steady-states x^s , are expressed in deviation form: the state variables x reflect the deviations from their respective steady-states for the variables $T_i, c_{A,i}, c_{B,i}, c_{C,i}$ across all three vessels. The control input u also consists of the heat flows (H_1, H_2, H_3) expressed in deviation form, adhering to the corresponding steady-state values indicated in Table I. The matrix E , which multiplies the disturbance vector d in equation (1), was chosen to be

the identity matrix.

The MPC configuration is set for a prediction horizon of $N = 20$ and a sampling time of $T_s = 0.1$ h. The weighting matrices are defined as $R = \text{diag}(1, 1, 1) \cdot 10^{-2}$ and $Q = \text{diag}(Q_1, Q_2, Q_3)$, where $Q_i = \text{diag}(3200, 1, 1, 1) \cdot 10^3$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$. The terminal penalty P and terminal set \mathbb{X}_N were computed during the implicit tube MPC construction by setting the option `LQRstability = 1`.

The closed-loop control results presented in this paper were generated using the MATLAB R2023b programming environment on a system equipped with an i5 1.7GHz CPU and 16GB RAM. The implicit tube MPC was developed utilizing the MPT+ toolbox, while optimization problems were addressed through YALMIP R20210331 [11], MPT 3.2.1 [12], with MOSEK 10.0.40 [25] acting as the solver.

Fig. 2: Scheme of system with two reactors and a separator [24].

C. Results and discussion

To demonstrate the benefits of the implicit tube MPC implementation via the MPT+ toolbox, the

Fig. 1: Closed-loop simulation of control of the reactor-separator benchmark – controlled variables: system states (solid blue), steady-state values (dashed green).

Fig. 3: Closed-loop simulation of control of the reactor-separator benchmark – manipulated variables: control inputs (solid blue), constraints (dashed red).

simulation of the closed-loop control for the large-scale reactor-separator system was performed in the presence of the bounded additive disturbance. The simulation starts with the initial conditions $x_1(0) = [-8.84, -0.12, -0.02, -0.01]^T$ for the first reactor, $x_2(0) = [-4.34, 0.01, -0.11, -0.03]^T$ for the second reactor and $x_3(0) = [-4.83, -0.09, -0.12, -0.04]^T$ for separator. Here, the vectors x_i represent the deviation variables for the temperature and concentrations of the reactant A and products B and C in the i -th vessel.

The resulting control trajectories are depicted in Fig. 1 for the state variables, i.e., $T_i, c_{Ai}, c_{Bi}, c_{Ci}$ across all three vessels, and in Fig. 3 for the control input variables H_i .

As shown in Fig. 1, the designed robust MPC successfully provided control inputs to bring the controlled variables to the unstable steady-state point safely. Furthermore, Fig. 3 demonstrates that the control inputs adhered to the constraints even in the presence of randomly generated disturbances from the predefined range.

From the computation point of view, the MPT+ toolbox formulated the implicit tube MPC formulation (13), with setup as stated in Section IV-B, in 16.5361 seconds. The complexity of the problem was 984 constraints and 60 optimization variables. The maximum, average, and minimum evaluation time of the optimization problem within the simulation was 0.1406, 0.0398, and 0.0156 seconds, respectively.

It is important to note that the original set-based tube MPC could not be developed due to significant numerical challenges associated with geometric set-based operations. Nevertheless, the implicit tube MPC was successfully designed and implemented for this large-scale system, see Fig. 1–3.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper addresses the problem of robust MPC design for complex large-scale systems in an efficient way by providing a user-friendly software package enabling the user to focus on the controller design, tuning, and validation. Notably, the paper introduced an extension of the MPT+ toolbox for designing implicit tube MPC policies within the MATLAB programming environment. A brief tutorial was provided, demonstrating how MPT+ facilitates the construction and simulation of implicit tube MPC. To illustrate the benefits of the presented package, the presented numerical examples demonstrated the successful implementation of the implicit tube MPC control strategy. With the recent state of the MPT+ toolbox, users are able to analyse both rigid and implicit tube MPC approaches.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is funded by the European Commission under the grant no. 101079342 (Fostering Opportunities Towards Slovak Excellence in Advanced Control for Smart Industries). The authors also gratefully acknowledge the contribution of the Scientific Grant Agency of the Slovak Republic under the grants 1/0490/23, 1/0297/22.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Maciejowski, *Predictive Control with Constraints*. London: Prentice Hall, 2000.
- [2] F. Borrelli, *Constrained Optimal Control of Linear and Hybrid Systems*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2017.
- [3] S. Qin and T. A. Badgwell, “A survey of industrial model predictive control technology,” *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 733–764, 2003.
- [4] D. Kouzoupis, G. Frison, A. Zanelli, and M. Diehl, “Recent advances in quadratic programming algorithms for nonlinear model predictive control,” *Vietnam J. Math.*, vol. 46, pp. 863–882, 2018.
- [5] B. Houska and J. Shi, “Distributed MPC with ALADIN—a tutorial,” in *2022 American Control Conference (ACC)*, pp. 358–363, 2022.
- [6] S. Lucia, A. Tătulea-Codrean, C. Schoppmeyer, and S. Engell, “Rapid development of modular and sustainable nonlinear model predictive control solutions,” *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 60, pp. 51–62, 2017.
- [7] MathWorks, “MPC Toolbox,” 2024. <https://www.mathworks.com/products/model-predictive-control.html>.
- [8] B. Houska, H. Ferreau, and M. Diehl, “ACADO Toolkit – an open source framework for automatic control and dynamic optimization,” *Optimal Control Applications and Methods*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 298–312, 2011.
- [9] J. Andersson, J. Gillis, G. Horn, J. Rawlings, and M. Diehl, “CasADi – a software framework for nonlinear optimization and optimal control,” *Mathematical Programming Computation*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–36, 2019.
- [10] Y. Chen, M. Bruschetta, E. Picotti, and A. Beghi, “MATMPC – A MATLAB based toolbox for real-time nonlinear model predictive control,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1811.08761, 2018.
- [11] J. Löfberg, “YALMIP : A Toolbox for Modeling and Optimization in MATLAB,” in *Proc. of the CACSD Conf.*, (Taipei, Taiwan), 2004.
- [12] M. Herceg, M. Kvasnica, C. Jones, and M. Morari, “Multi-parametric toolbox 3.0,” in *2013 European Control Conference*, pp. 502–510, 2013.
- [13] M. Kvasnica, B. Takács, J. Holaza, and D. Ingole, “Reachability analysis and control synthesis for uncertain linear systems in MPT,” in *Proceedings of the 8th IFAC Symposium on Robust Control Design* (M. Fikar, ed.), no. 8, (Bratislava, Slovak Republic), pp. 302–307, Elsevier, July 8–11, 2015.
- [14] D. Mayne, M. Seron, and S. Raković, “Robust model predictive control of constrained linear systems with bounded disturbances,” *Automatica*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 219–224, 2005.
- [15] S. Raković and D. Mayne, “A simple tube controller for efficient robust model predictive control of constrained linear discrete time systems subject to bounded disturbances,” *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 241–246, 2005. 16th IFAC World Congress.
- [16] S. V. Raković, B. Kouvaritakis, R. Findeisen, and M. Cannon, “Homothetic tube model predictive control,” *Automatica*, vol. 48, no. 8, pp. 1631–1638, 2012.
- [17] S. V. Raković, W. S. Levine, and B. Açikmese, “Elastic tube model predictive control,” in *2016 American Control Conference (ACC)*, pp. 3594–3599, 2016.
- [18] D. Mayne, S. Raković, R. Findeisen, and F. Allgöwer, “Robust output feedback model predictive control of constrained linear systems,” *Automatica*, vol. 42, no. 7, pp. 1217–1222, 2006.
- [19] D. Limon, I. Alvarado, T. Alamo, and E. Camacho, “Robust tube-based MPC for tracking of constrained linear systems with additive disturbances,” *Journal of Process Control*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 248–260, 2010.
- [20] K. Wang, Y. Jiang, J. Oravec, M. Villanueva, and B. Houska, “Parallel explicit tube model predictive control,” in *58th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, 58, (Nice, France), pp. 7696–7701, December 11–13, 2019 2019.
- [21] S. Raković, “The implicit rigid tube model predictive control,” *Automatica*, vol. 157, p. 111234, 2023.
- [22] J. Holaza, L. Galčíková, J. Oravec, and M. Kvasnica, “A software package for mpc design and tuning: Mpt+,” in *62nd IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, (Singapore), pp. 5682–5689, IEEE, December 13–15 2023.
- [23] S. Rakovic, E. Kerrigan, K. Kouramas, and D. Mayne, “Invariant approximations of the minimal robust positively invariant set,” *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 406–410, 2005.
- [24] L. Grüne, F. Allgöwer, R. Findeisen, J. Fischer, D. Groß, U. D. Hanebeck, B. Kern, M. A. Müller, J. Pannek, M. Reble, *et al.*, “Distributed and networked model predictive control,” *Control Theory of Digitally Networked Dynamic Systems*, pp. 111–167, 2014.
- [25] M. ApS, *The MOSEK optimization toolbox for MATLAB manual. Version 10.1.*, 2024.